

Thai LGBTQ+ Colloquials Through the Lens of Construction Grammar

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1. Introduction

Language, as a dynamic and evolving entity, reflects the nuances and identities of its speakers. In the vibrant tapestry of linguistic diversity, colloquials are a fascinating facet, often distinct from formal language. Colloquials are not merely slang; they encompass a wide range of linguistic constructions that encapsulate the authentic expressions and shared meanings within particular groups. To better understand and explore the intricacies of these colloquials within the Thai LGBTQ+ community, we turn to the framework of construction grammar (Goldberg 1995).

Construction grammar provides an apt lens for this exploration. According to Goldberg (2003), a construction is defined as “a form–meaning pair” (F-S) and represents a unit of knowledge, emphasizing the inseparability of form and meaning in language. Furthermore, construction grammar introduces the critical criterion of non-predictability, acknowledging that a construction incorporates elements of form or meaning that cannot be deduced purely through linguistic analysis. In the context of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials, constructions become a fundamental element for examining their unique linguistic expressions and the cultural meanings they convey.

The data for this investigation were gathered from the LGBTQ+ vlogger group known as “Hiw Whee,” operating on their official YouTube channel, “Hiwwhee Official.” The group is composed of five main characters: Nutt Nisamane, Eclair Juepak, Alie Blackcobra, Mix Chaleomsri, and Erk Charrissa. This selection of data sources is motivated by the extensive and diverse database at their disposal. The Hiw Whee vlogger group celebrates a decade of existence in December 2022, marking their enduring influence in the world of Thai LGBTQ+ content creation. Their content reflects the natural and diverse use of LGBTQ+ colloquials in the Thai context, as they engage in authentic conversations, often involving larger team members working behind the scenes who occasionally make on-camera appearances. Each member of the group embodies unique characters, contributing to a rich variety of linguistic expressions that mirror the diversity within Thai LGBTQ+ community.

Employing a methodology that combines conversational analysis, close reading, and critical discourse analysis under the framework of construction grammar, this research seeks to categorize the most common Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials with their variations based on pragmatic use. The colloquials

are also analyzed based on their syntactic structures, semantics, and collocates. This comprehensive approach allows for a deeper exploration of the intricacies of these colloquials, going beyond mere linguistic form to unveil the cultural, social, and identity-related facets they embody.

This paper sheds light on the underexplored terrain of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials and their construction-based linguistic expressions. As these colloquials continue to influence and guide the way the public uses language, this study presents a crucial opportunity to comprehend their nuances and cultural significance within the broader linguistic landscape. In doing so, it adds a valuable perspective to our understanding of the dynamic interplay between language, identity, and community within the Thai LGBTQ+ context.

2. Not All LGBTQ+ Colloquials Are Constructions

In the quest to unravel the intricacies of LGBTQ+ colloquials within the framework of construction grammar, it is imperative to establish a clear understanding of what constitutes a construction. Goldberg’s well-known criterion of non-predictability is a foundational aspect of this definition. However, it is crucial to recognize that construction grammar offers a more nuanced perspective on language structure, incorporating various other criteria that help us identify constructions. Hilpert (2019) has proposed additional criteria, including questions such as, “Does the expression carry non-compositional meaning? Does the expression have idiosyncratic constraints? Does the expression have collocational preferences?” These criteria enable us to differentiate between true linguistic constructions and other forms of language.

Linguistic constructions are essentially form–meaning pairs where the form and meaning are inherently linked. To be considered a construction, an expression must exhibit non-predictable aspects, highlighting the inseparability of form and meaning. While colloquials within the LGBTQ+ community often manifest this inseparability, not all colloquials qualify as constructions. Take, for instance, the following examples:

(1) เรือง	เยอะ	(2) หัว	จะ	ปวด
/rueng/	/yoe/	/hua/	/cha/	/puad/
stories	a lot	head	will	pain
‘Too much’		‘There will be a headache.’		

These phrases, although frequently used in the LGBTQ+ community, do not meet the criteria that identify a construction, particularly Hilpert’s framework.

Firstly, the criterion of non-compositional meaning asks whether an expression carries meaning that cannot be derived through a straightforward combination of its component parts. “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ and “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/ do not meet this criterion. The meaning of “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ is a straightforward combination of its constituent words: “rueng” meaning “stories” and “yoe” meaning “too much.” Similarly, “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/ is a concatenation of /hua/ “head,” /cha/ “will,” and /puad/ “pain”. In both cases, the meanings can be easily deduced by understanding the individual words, so they lack the non-compositional aspect essential to constructions.

Secondly, constructions are characterized by idiosyncratic constraints, indicating that they may have specific grammatical or syntactic limitations that make them unique. However, “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ and “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/ do not exhibit any idiosyncratic constraints. They follow standard grammatical structures and can be used in a wide range of contexts without notable syntactic restrictions.

Lastly, the criterion of collocational preferences is vital in identifying constructions. Constructions often display particular word pairings or collocations that are not easily replaceable with synonymous words. In the case of “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ and “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/, it is not that they merely exhibit collocational preferences, but they are strictly used as they are. Attempts to alter or replace any of their constituent elements with synonymous words or phrases would result in linguistic incongruity. For instance, trying to substitute “เรื่องน้อย” /rueng noi/ (too few stories) for “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ to mean something being too little or too simple simply does not make sense. Similarly, the /tao cha puad/, which translates to “there will be pain in the feet,” lacks the naturalness of “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/. These examples underscore the inflexibility of these colloquials in terms of their collocational preferences, as no element within them can be replaced with any other words without causing a disruption in meaning and fluency.

This inflexibility in terms of collocational preferences is noteworthy as it serves as one of the criteria to differentiate linguistic constructions from other forms of language. Notably, this criterion will be very useful as we explore LGBTQ+ colloquials in the next sections of this essay. It will become apparent that some elements in these colloquials can be replaced with alternative words, while others remain fixed, underscoring the creative and productive nature of LGBTQ+ colloquials. These colloquials often allow for modifications, resulting in various expressions with slightly different connotations, reflecting the fluidity and adaptability of language within the LGBTQ+ community.

In light of these observations, it becomes evident that not all LGBTQ+ colloquials fit the criteria of constructions within the framework of construction grammar. “เรื่องเยอะ” /rueng yoe/ and “หัวจะปวด” /hua cha puad/, despite their frequent use within the LGBTQ+ community, are not

constructions due to their lack of predictability, non-compositional meaning, idiosyncratic constraints, and collocational preferences. To further our exploration, we will focus on LGBTQ+ colloquials that meet the construction criteria. By narrowing our focus to these colloquials, we can gain deeper insights into their linguistic intricacies and their significance within the LGBTQ+ community.

3. Three Categories of Thai LGBTQ+ Colloquials

The linguistic landscape of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials is a vibrant and dynamic one, intimately intertwined with the unique characteristics of the LGBTQ+ people in Thailand. In this chapter, we will explore different colloquials while also keeping in mind the correlation between the distinct features of Thai LGBTQ+ individuals and their language use. It is essential to acknowledge that nearly all LGBTQ+ colloquials in Thailand are innovations by members of this community (especially gays, transwomen, ladyboys, or shemales.) These colloquials gradually find their way into the broader public's vocabulary. In Thailand, gays, transwomen, ladyboys, or shemales are known for their flamboyant personalities and unconventional preferences. As a result, many of these colloquials revolve around the premise of pointing out and questioning the extremity of actions, offering critiques, and issuing demands to others. It is worth noting that the main functions of these colloquials are not to criticize, belittle, or demand, as the literal meaning might suggest. Instead, they often act as facilitators in conversations, showing intimacy and camaraderie within the LGBTQ+ community.

Martin Hilpert's perspective on Construction Grammar, as highlighted in his work (2019), emphasizes that this framework goes beyond the mere analysis of syntactic structure and semantics. It includes more delicate elements such as pitch and intonation. In the context of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials, we find that some of these linguistic expressions are accompanied by specific pitch patterns and intonations that further enhance their communicative impact.

To categorize the rich tapestry of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials, we have identified three main categories based on the intentions and purposes of the speakers.

3.1. Expressive and Exaggerative Colloquials

This category encompasses colloquials that serve as a means of vividly expressing emotions, opinions, or reactions. These colloquials often involve flamboyant and exaggerated language, reflecting the LGBTQ+ community's vibrant and expressive nature. They are used to amplify statements, create emphasis, and highlight the emotional intensity of a message.

(3) ... มาก
.../mak/
...a lot

(4) ... เกิน
.../koen/
too...

(5) ... เวย์
.../woe/
over...

According to the Thai Dictionary, Royal Institute Edition 2011, the term “มาก” /mak/ is classified as an adjective signifying “a lot.” It is typically employed to modify nouns, as seen in examples like “น้ำมาก” /nam mak/, meaning “a lot of water,” or “คนมาก” /kon mak/, signifying “a lot of people.” Similarly, “เกิน” /koen/ functions as an adjective, indicating excess or surpassing a specified limit. It finds application in contexts such as “เกินขนาด” /koen kanad/, denoting “more than the limited size,” or “เกินเวลา” /koen wela/, representing “more than the limited time.” In contrast, “เวย์” /woe/ is a spoken language colloquialism, borrowed from the English word “over.” However, according to Collins Dictionary, it does not encompass any adverbial usage for modifying adjectives. Hence, the application of these words in this unconventional manner as an adverb modifying an adjective, as seen in the LGBTQ+ colloquials, represents a construction. The structure of these constructions is simple. It consists of two primary elements: an adjective closely followed by an emphatic modifying adverb “เกิน” /koen/, “มาก” /mak/, or “เวย์” /woe/. The role of the emphatic modifier is to provide an interpretation of “a lot,” “too much,” or “over the top,” while the adjective slot remains adaptable. The pronunciation of emphatic modifiers are typically prolonged and stressed to enhance their expressive impact.

For instance, in a clip featuring Mix Chaleomsri¹, around the 0.00-0.03 minute mark, her camera person spotted a massive crayfish, to which she exclaimed, “กึ่งตัวใหญ่มาก” /kang tua yai mak/, signifying “What a huge crayfish!” Additionally, while holding an oversized lobster, Mix used the expression “ใหญ่เวย์” /yai woe/, conveying “So big.”

In another instance, during Erk Charrissa's video² at the 2.06-minute mark, Eclair cast her eyes on the food and remarked, “น่ากินมาก” /na kin mak/, which translates to “Looks yummy!” Later, at the 2.26-minute mark, the group engaged in a discussion about their favorite foods. However, Eclair’s choice of food was not included in the video, prompting her to remark, “น้อยด์มาก” /noi mak/, meaning “So paranoid.”

In Hiw Whee group video³ [07.18], when Toon discussed her desire to have some imperfections during her childhood, Nutt aptly acknowledged Toon’s sentiment by stating, “อยากให้ดูเป็นคนบ้าง มันนางฟ้าเกิน” /yak hai du pen kon bang man nang fa goen/, meaning “wishing to appear more ordinary

¹ <https://youtu.be/iCCcC4uQtng?si=S1VCjqquS8TTTEN>

² https://youtu.be/4z45gWC_jEE?si=MQ4jPwGuhTN4BMJf

³ <https://youtu.be/DeKmZWY4I04?si=cBnPx2yiXNqIDl3w>

because you were too angelic.” This particular instance revealed a less common collocational pattern, as emphatic modifiers are used in conjunction with a noun. Notably, in this context, “นางฟ้า” /nang fa/ typically signifying an angel takes on a different interpretation, being coerced to fit the syntactic context as it is followed with an adverb “เกิน” /koen/, thus transforming “นางฟ้า” as a noun “angel” into an adjective “angelic.” Subsequently, Eclair joined the conversation by commenting on Toon’s desire for pimples and short eyesight [07.24], expressing, “ดูไร้สาระเกิน” /du rai sara goen/, meaning “That sounded so nonsensical.”

The unconventional use of emphatic modifying adjectives “เกิน” /koen/, “มาก” /mak/, and “เวอร์” /woe/ as adverbs in LGBTQ+ colloquials makes them an intriguing linguistic construction. These linguistic nuances are regularly and predominantly utilized in LGBTQ+ conversations, serving as a means to convey a broad spectrum of emotions, with a particular emphasis on accentuating extremeness within their interactions. These linguistic constructions enhance the depth and richness of their communication, emphasizing the intensity and significance of their expressions.

3.2. Critique and Challenge Colloquials

In this category, we encounter colloquials that are employed to critique or contest particular actions or behaviors. These expressions frequently involve an element of questioning the logic or appropriateness of certain choices and decisions. Intriguingly, these colloquials, despite their literal meanings, play a unique role in facilitating communication by infusing it with a sense of enjoyment and smoothness. It is important to note that this group of colloquials exhibits a varying degree of strength, ranging from merely pointing out certain aspects to more pointedly criticizing actions or behaviors. The first category includes Example 6, and the second category, with a stronger and more pronounced meaning, is demonstrated in Examples 7 to 9.

- (6) รับ บท นาง...
 /rab/ /bot/ /nang/...
 get role miss...
 ‘Took a role of...’

The colloquial featured in Example 6 finds its origins in a distinct role assignment commonly seen in Thai telenovelas, notably the roles of “นางเอก” /nang ek/, signifying a virtuous leading actress, and “นางร้าย” /nang rai/, representing a malevolent leading actress. The “นางเอก” /nang ek/ embodies characteristics of naivety, an inability to outsmart others, or a disposition to yield to oppressors, whereas the “นางร้าย” /nang rai/ embodies qualities of meanness and intimidation. Over time, the roles

became more productive and could be replaced with other words and utilized in various contexts. This colloquial construction is used in a humorous manner to depict a person’s actions, especially when those actions are perceived as uncommon or slightly inappropriate within a specific context, diverging from their typical behavior or routine.

As an example of the widespread use of this colloquial, even Khaosod, a prominent Thai daily newspaper with national circulation, featured a news headline in October 2023, stating, “แก๊งหัวหวี... รับบทบาทโอน...” /kang hiw wi rab bot nang on/, which translates to “Hiw Whee group... took a role of a transferer (financial supporter)...” Apart from verbs like “โอน” /on/ for “transfer,” the role designation can also be customized with adjectives, like “เสือก” /sueak/ “obtrusive” as in “รับบทนางเสือก” /rab bot nang sueak/ “You took a role of Mrs. Obtrusive (being inappropriately curious about personal stories).” showing flexibility and creativity in its application.

(7) แล้ว	จะ...	เพื่อ	(8) เอา	อะไร	มา...	อะ
/law/	/cha/...	/puea/	/aw/	/a rai/	/ma/...	/a/
already	would...	for	take	what	come	Q
‘Why did you... for?’			‘What made you so...?’			
(9) แล้ว	จะ...	ทำไม	ก่อน			
/law/	/cha/...	/tam mai/	/kon/			
already	would...	why	before			
‘Why did you... in the first place?’						

Shifting the focus from mere addressing to a more pronounced critique of actions and behaviors, the second group of colloquials underscores an intriguing transformation in its usage. This group of colloquials is characterized by its capacity to convey a certain degree of criticism and frequently carries an undertone of anger. These expressions are typically reserved for intense or emotionally charged situations, although it is worth noting that Example 8 can also be employed in a humorous and playful manner. Example 7 and 9 share similar meanings, to the extent that the same words can seamlessly fit into both constructions. For instance, phrases like “แล้วจะพูดเพื่อ” /law cha pud puea/, which translates to “Why did you say that?” and “แล้วจะพูดทำไมก่อน” /law cha pud tam mai kon/, meaning “Why did you say that in the first place?” are employed to criticize individuals when they make statements that are perceived as irrelevant, illogical, or unhelpful.

On the other hand, Example 8 is often used in conjunction with the adjective “มัน” /man/, meaning “confident,” as in “เอาอะไรมามันอะ” /aw a rai ma man a/, which translates to “What makes you

so confident?” This construction is typically directed at someone displaying an excess of self-assuredness. However, when used in conjunction with alternative adjectives, this colloquial often conveys a whimsical tone, typically followed by laughter. For example, when preparing a meal for ten people, yet the ingredients are insufficient, one might exclaim, “เอาอะไรมาพออะ” /aw a rai ma po a/, humorously signifying, “this can never be enough.” Similarly, when planning a trip to a frigid destination but having lightweight clothing, someone could say, “เอาอะไรมาอุ่นอะ” /aw a rai ma un a/, playfully expressing, “this can never be warm enough.” Both instances reflect a playful exaggeration and a touch of humor.

3.3. Demands and Assertions Colloquials

Colloquials within this category are marked by their assertive nature, serving as a means to articulate demands and express desires. Structurally, this group of colloquials adopts the form of an imperative sentence.

- (10) ฟัง นะ
 /fang/ /na/
 listen [PARTICLE]
 ‘Listen!’

Example 10, “ฟังนะ” /fang na/, which translates to “Listen!” in English, serves a unique function. It goes beyond the literal act of instructing a listener to listen to a specific sound or message. Instead, it is employed to capture a listener’s attention, urging them to focus on what is about to be communicated.

In a specific instance from Erk Charrissa’s clip⁴ at the 1.24-minute mark, where she celebrated her 100th episode with palpable excitement and a spirited, loud delivery, the colloquial “ฟังนะ” took on a particular significance. With a relatively low occurrence of guests in her show, her enthusiastic manner prompted Eclair to suggest calming down by asking, “กดดันอะไร” /kod dan a rai/, which translates to “What are you stressed about?” Mix also chimed in with, “ฟังนะ เราเป็นเพื่อนกัน” /fang na raw pen puean kan/, meaning “Listen! We are friends,” supplementing Eclair’s advice. In the same clip [6.16], when Mix expressed discomfort due to the heat in the celebration room, Erk used “ฟังนะ” to direct everyone’s attention and explain the situation, stating, “ฟังนะ ปกติห้องนี้ไม่เคยร้อน” /fang na pokati hong ni mai koei ron/, which means “Listen! This room never gets hot.” Mix said “ฟังนะ” /fang na/

⁴ https://youtu.be/4z45gWC_jEE?si=MQ4jPwGuhTN4BMJf

again during minute 13.56 when she explained a situation to exemplify that Nutt can not conclude a discussing topic.

To highlight the frequency of “ฟังนะ” /fang na/, let us consider some more examples from a Hiw Whee group video⁵ [14.39], where Mix and Eclair playfully teased Toon for not being as active as she used to be. Toon attempted to offer an explanation by humorously saying, “มิกซ์ฟังนะ เพิ่งไปหาหมอมา กระดูกพรุนทุกจุด” /mix fang na poeng pai ha mo ma kra duk prun tuk chud/, which translates to “Mix, listen! I just went to a doctor, and all my bones were porous.” Toon then tossed a ball to Eclair, challenging her to partake in something adventurous. In response, Eclair playfully repeated the joke [14.55], remarking, “ฟังนะ ไปหาหมอมา ไชมันอุดตัน” /fang na pai ha mo ma kai man ud tan/, meaning “Listen! I went to a doctor, and my veins are full of fats.”

In line with Auer’s insights (2005, 2009,) “ฟังนะ” /fang na/ also functions as a projecting element in conversation. Speakers actively employ it to create certain expectations within their listeners, guiding the course of the interaction and emphasizing specific points.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

The exploration of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials, through the lens of construction grammar, reveals a complex tapestry of linguistic creativity and cultural significance within the LGBTQ+ community. These colloquials serve as a unique and dynamic form of expression, reflecting the rich diversity within the community.

This contribution to linguistic diversity in society is rooted in the LGBTQ+ community’s inherent traits of creativity. As these colloquials continue to evolve and influence broader language use, they embody the expressive and innovative spirit of the LGBTQ+ community, allowing its members to articulate a wide range of emotions, including humor and critique. The LGBTQ+ community has fostered a space where the boundaries of language are pushed to the extreme, making language an integral part of their identity.

From a sociological perspective, the use of these colloquials may result from the LGBTQ+ community’s attempt to emphasize their uniqueness, distinguishing themselves from individuals outside the group, while also fostering solidarity within their own community. These colloquials are not just linguistic constructs; they are tools for establishing connections, expressing support, and cementing a sense of shared identity.

Moreover, within the broader societal context, the creative use of language within the LGBTQ+ community can also be seen as a response to the oppressions or restrictions that society may

⁵ <https://youtu.be/DeKmZWY4I04?si=cBnPx2yiXNqIDI3w>

consciously or unconsciously impose on them. Language becomes a powerful means of resistance, enabling the LGBTQ+ community to shape their own narrative, reclaim derogatory terms, and assert their identities.

The diversity of Thai LGBTQ+ colloquials exemplifies how language evolves within specific cultural and social niches. It is essential to recognize that not all colloquials fit the criteria of constructions, but this variation adds to the linguistic richness and adaptability within the LGBTQ+ community. The three categories of colloquials, including expressive and exaggerative, critique and challenge, and demands and assertions, showcase the dynamic nature of language within this community. Each category serves distinct functions, from amplifying emotions to critiquing actions and asserting demands, reflecting the multifaceted nature of LGBTQ+ interactions.

In essence, this study provides a valuable perspective on the interplay between language, identity, and community within the Thai LGBTQ+ context. As these colloquials continue to shape the linguistic landscape, it is crucial to appreciate their role in fostering communication, solidarity, and self-expression within the LGBTQ+ community while also challenging societal norms and expectations. The LGBTQ+ community in Thailand, through its creative linguistic expressions, has carved a space for itself in the broader cultural and linguistic milieu, contributing to the ongoing evolution of the Thai language. Understanding and appreciating these colloquials is not only a linguistic endeavor but also a means of acknowledging the resilience and strength of a marginalized community.

The future of research on LGBTQ+ colloquials lies in constructing a dedicated corpus that encapsulates the diverse language use within this community. This corpus will serve as a foundational resource for linguistic analyses, particularly statistical approaches. Researchers can delve into frequency analysis and collocation analysis, offering insights into the most prevalent LGBTQ+ colloquials and their grammatical associations. Additionally, sociolinguistic exploration can unveil linguistic variations among different subgroups and regions, shedding light on the intricate relationships between language and identity within the LGBTQ+ community. Diachronic analysis can track the historical evolution of colloquials, while using the corpus to understand the ever-changing landscape of LGBTQ+ language. Ultimately, such a corpus can also inform language education and cultural inclusivity initiatives, ensuring that LGBTQ+ language diversity is acknowledged and celebrated.

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Appendix

YouTube Channels

- Hiw Whee group: <https://www.youtube.com/@HiwwheeOfficial>
- Nutt Nisamanee: <https://www.youtube.com/@NisamaneeNutt>
- Mix Chaleomsri: <https://www.youtube.com/@Chaleomsri>
- Alie Blackcobra: <https://www.youtube.com/@AlieBlackcobra>
- Eclair Juepak: <https://www.youtube.com/@juepak>
- Erk Charrissa: <https://www.youtube.com/@Erkiiz>